

MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF SUBSTANCES

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ANNOTATION

In this article, it is observed that many substances (for example, iron, nickel, cobalt) become magnetized when they are placed in a magnetic field or when a current passes through them. They create a magnetic field around them like a magnet.

Key words: Magnetic field, coil, galvanometer, magnetic absorption, paramagnetic, ferromagnetic

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье наблюдается, что многие вещества (например, железо, никель, кобальт) намагничиваются, когда их помещают в магнитное поле или когда через них проходит ток. Они создают вокруг себя магнитное поле, как магнит.

Ключевые слова: Магнитное поле, катушка, гальванометр, магнитное поглощение, парамагнетик, ферромагнетик.

Substances that become magnetized under the influence of a magnetic field are called magnets.

In order to evaluate the magnetic field inside the coil, the following demonstration experiment can be conducted. An overview of the demonstration device is shown in Figure 1a. The demonstration device consists of a current source, two coils, cores made of different materials, an ammeter and a switch.

*a**b**1-rasm*

If the experiment is repeated by inserting metal cores of different nature into the coil without changing the voltage, we will see different changes in the deflection of the galvanometer arrow due to the different changes in the induction of the magnetic field inside it (1- Figure b).

The induction of the magnetic field generated inside the coil depends on the nature of the introduced substance, i.e.:

$$B = m \cdot B_0. (1-6)$$

Therefore, the induction of the magnetic field (B) created by the current coil in a medium is directly proportional to the magnetic field induction (B₀) created by it in a vacuum, and also depends on the type of medium (m) will be If we find m from the expression (1– 6):

$$m = B. (1-7)$$

0 m in this equation is called the magnetic permeability of the medium. It depends only on the nature of the medium, and indicates how many times the field induction in the medium differs from the magnetic field induction in vacuum.

All substances found in nature are divided into three types depending on their magnetic absorption. These are: diamagnetic, paramagnetic and ferromagnetic.

Substances with magnetic absorption less than unity ($m < 1$) are called diamagnetic. Gold, silver, copper, zinc and some gases are diamagnetic. Diamagnetics introduced into the magnetic field weaken it. When a magnetic field is brought closer to such substances, they move away from the field (Fig. 1.6).

1.6-rasm.

For substances with a magnetic susceptibility slightly greater than unity ($\mu > 1$), are called paramagnetic.

Paramagnetic substances include platinum, aluminum, chromium, manganese, and oxygen. Paramagnetics introduced into the magnetic field partially strengthen the field.

Substances with magnetic susceptibility greater than unity ($\mu \gg 1$) are called ferromagnetic. Iron, nickel, cobalt and some of their alloys are ferromagnetic. Ferromagnets introduced into the magnetic field strengthen it.

When objects made of such substances are placed in a magnetic field, they approach the field (Fig. 1.7).

1.7-rasm.

In conclusion, we can say that although ferromagnets are not very abundant in nature, they are widely used in modern technology. For example, cores of transformers, current generators, electric motors and other devices are made of ferromagnetic materials. Recently, permanent magnets have been widely used in medicine. They are being made into a bracelet that can be worn as a blood pressure lowering device.

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